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MANUSCRIPT PREPARATION INSTRUCTIONS

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Nowadays timber buildings are present worldwide, because the use of sustainable materials is encouraged both from governments and from public opinion. Thus, a chance is to increase the number of timber multi-story buildings. Nevertheless, there is still a huge need for gaining the trust of construction companies, local governments and the general public as well as to spread the information concerning the possibility of timber multi-story construction. Therefore, a much stronger cooperation is necessary with regard to R&D, education, knowledge transfer and best practice issues. The creation of awareness and reduction of prejudices and barriers for high volume wooden constructions are main challenges.

Therefore, in this paper, an overview of past international progresses related to multi-story timber structures is presented and the new Interreg ITA-AT BIGWOOD project proposals are depicted.

Keywords: wooden building; energy efficiency; State of the Art; sound and thermal insulation

1. Introduction

The aim of this research is to provide an overview of the projects carried out and in progress that address the issue of wooden building, with attention to the timber supply chain, the energy efficiency and to the multi-storey wooden structures' potential. The interest is focused on analysing how the BIGWOOD project fits into European projects by describing what characterizes and distinguishes it from those already in progress or already completed. The project "Interreg - BIGWOOD" aims to reduce barriers and prejudices on multi-story wooden buildings through the creation of design awareness. The need to focus on these issues stems from the need to develop research, education, knowledge transfer and best practices to raise awareness among stakeholders, the public and relevant organizations. For this reason, BIGWOOD wants to create:

- an interregional network to increase the use of wood for high volume projects
- the experimentation and validation of criteria and guidelines for the realization of multi-story wooden buildings
- a training and information space for the dissemination of issues related to the realization of multi-story wooden buildings
- the realization of 3 mock-ups: one on a 1:1 scale and two of medium and small size (1:5 and 1:20) all realized at the NOI Techpark in Bozen/Bolzano.

From the side of knowledge dissemination, BIGWOOD proposes to concatenate the objectives and to develop not only on the dissemination of knowledge among practitioners in the sector but also on addressing a much wider audience. Furthermore, it wants to make clearer and simpler to those in the sector:

- the necessary standards to be achieved both for thermal and acoustic comfort
 - the necessary standards for seismic and fire safety
 - to create a communication network between projects and companies in the construction of wood.
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The focus is to understand the connection points, similarities and intersections, but also to highlight individualities and differences between the several projects. By this assessment it is possible to pay attention on how BIGWOOD fits into the different European projects that have been carried out so far or that are still ongoing,

2. European timber supply chain and construction projects

In this section, project that have similar topics and aims of BIGWOOD are analysed. The topics involved are:

- implementation of territorial supply chains,
- dissemination focusing on sustainable timber construction,
- energy efficiency and the design of multi-story wooden buildings,
- the construction of a demonstration building on a natural scale.

The evaluation of the most important projects in Europe are catalogued based on the topics addressed for completed and ongoing projects.

The objectives achieved and concretized are described only for those completed.

2.1 European projects for the creation of a wood supply chain and for the dissemination of knowledge.

In this Section are analysed four projects that stand out among all on the theme of the timber supply chain and the dissemination of knowledge.

2.1.1 Interregional test and promotion center for the wood sector - EUROWOOD IV

This project is also commonly known as "EUROWOOD IV" (1). This European Interreg project between France and Belgium held between 2008 and 2012. It aims to strengthen the multifunctional role of forests, ensure territorial dialogue, improve the competitiveness of the companies involved and implement a communication strategy to raise public awareness of the importance of natural resources. The project involved 19 local forest-wood sector partners that came together to develop a cross-border program upstream, downstream and across the board. Work was carried out on the management of cross-border forest areas and support for elected representatives of forest communities upstream of the sector. Downstream of the sector there was work on: support, technical advice and information for businesses. A cross-border platform has been realized for the marketing of logs, the development of the wood energy island, the promotion of wood to the general public and decision-makers, and the organization of meetings and conferences. The partnership involved the actors of the wood sector, through the mutualization of technical means and the exchange of know-how and experience feedback. Has been established common tools to include the actions in a framework of cross-border and national exchange and partnership. Furthermore, has been carried out a strategy throughout the cross-border territory for increasing information and awareness raising. The transversal system described has developed the construction of a supply chain and communication network between suppliers, designers and technology partners. The composite network of connections and close cooperation have also made it easier for partners to achieve the necessary standards, certifications and compliance with regulatory requirements. Has been realized several awards, an exhibition and the collection of documentation on wood, through an online library to which the practitioners who participated in the project had access.

2.1.2 Interregional V-A Spain - France - Andorra (POCTEFA) COOPERANDO CON MADERA

This project, also known as "COOPWOOD" (2), is similar at the first examined for the didactic - communicative approach. The project started in 2014 and is scheduled to end in March 2020.

"COOPWOOD" aims to promote cross-border cooperation between the actors involved in vocational training in the wood sector and its activity, allowing a substantial improvement of the contents, methods, tools and training offers. The aim is to improve the qualification levels and skills of the different actors in the wood sector, mainly trainers, students and technicians. It wants to encourage a new revival for a declining sector, unable to adapt to new market trends and society in general. The strategy adopted envisages: the developing tools for knowledge, an analysis and implementation of existing legislation on both sides of the border, improving mutual knowledge of the current situation of the sector in terms of employment and training, enabling the recognition of qualifications and accreditation of professional skills and the creation of the first observatory for employment and training, integrating innovation into training processes, improving access to information.

The objectives have been achieved with the creation of a support network between the bordering areas between Spain and France. This aim has been achieved:

- with a cross-border working group in the field of building and wood construction training,
- by analysing the training analysis in Spain and France,
- by creating a legal matrix guide for work in the wood sector between the two countries,
 - through the drafting of methodological guidelines for application in active - collaborative models in the wood sector.

2.1.3 TRIPLE WOOD - sustainable wood building culture in the Alpine region.

"TRIPLE WOOD" (3) is a project for the divulgation of knowledge and awareness of wood building in the Alpine region. It is started in 2018 and ended in February 2020. The project co-financed by the European Union through the Preparatory Action Fund of the Alpine Region (ARPAF). The numerous partners from the region and the public administration, have settled two main goals:

- increasing the acceptance of wood in the design of new structures and the repair of old buildings,
- developing and disseminating methods to evaluate, strengthen and monitor them.

The multidisciplinary vision of the problems and innovative solutions have allowed the creation of synergies between stakeholders. The structure of the project has also provided an effective way to discuss and disseminate the results of ongoing projects in this research area to European industry. The final purpose was to increase the confidence of designers, authorities and end-users in the safe, durable and efficient use of wood and, consequently, to increase its use in construction. The didactic program has produced courses on the topics of timber construction systems, seismic and fire safety. The courses are aimed both at technicians, with no previous experience in the specific field of timber construction, and experts. In addition, has been drawn up a final collection of the results of the experiences, a didactical exhibition and of the training courses. In the final collection are included useful case studies for each branch of planning and architecture.

2.1.4 KnoWood: Knowledge Alliance for Sustainable Mid-Rise and Tall Wooden Buildings.

"KnoWood" (4) is a project started in 2019 and that will end in 2021. The project partners are 11, of which 5 are prestigious universities. The lead partner is VIA University (Denmark). The new-born project aims to meet future needs in higher education. It wants also to include entrepreneurial approaches to teaching and learning, innovation, sustainability, transnational and transdisciplinary understanding in sustainable medium and high-rise timber buildings. For these reasons, the project aims to increase sustainable forestry growth, employment in the timber construction industry, a major reduction of greenhouse gases, create new innovative and sustainable knowledge and academic courses. The project plans to promote cooperation and innovation between European higher education institutions, researchers,

business partners, associations, networks and society in general. Furthermore, wants to promote the design and the construction of medium and high height wooden buildings. The newly created project is taking shape, but of course it has yet to materialize most of its aims.

2.2 European projects for the realization of a wood supply chain, for the diffusion of knowledge, for the awareness of the energy efficiency of multi-story wooden structures.

Three projects have deepened the issue of energy efficiency in addition to the topics previously addressed.

2.2.1 Interreg V-A Belgium - France (France - Wallonie - Vlaanderen): Project 4 - Skills development - Acquiring the right technical skills.

The project is also known as "FormaWood" (5). It aims to develop a wood supply chain, diffuse knowledge and in addition wants to widen the energy efficiency characteristics of wooden building. The project starts in 2014 and will end in September 2020. It involves numerous wood companies in Wallonia and Hauts-de-France. "FormaWood". It is designed for an audience of architects, engineers, design offices, contractors, employees of construction companies, trainers, students of colleges and technical high schools, teachers and researchers at universities and research centres. For this achievement has been done:

- a program of training modules according to the needs of the territory,
- the provision of a project management support unit,
- a study trip abroad,
- the realization of teaching aids for architectural work and wood skills
- a teaching aid for acoustic comfort in wooden constructions.

Attention has been paid, in the architectural teaching aid, to new buildings, to interventions aimed at the renovation of existing buildings and to architectural harmonization. The second didactic tool is represented by six technical data sheets on topics in wood construction skills and good practices developed by the project partners:

- On the insulation of walls under renovation in according to the BBC or RT 2012 standards for France, PEB for Belgium and comparing them with the European passive design standards
- On the construction systems and construction techniques of building systems
- On the implementation of construction details for passive and energy-efficient construction
- On the insulation of sloping roofs under renovation in according to the BBC standards, RT 2012 for France, PEB for Belgium, comparing the European approach of passive house
- On the importance of the design and implementation of construction knots
- On the choice and implementation of wood cladding, the characterization of the materials used, the execution of the work and the processing of unique points.

"FormaWood" has produced, in addition, a documentation describing the complex challenge of sound insulation for wooden buildings. In this latest are showed both French and Belgian standards.

2.2.2 NERO: Cost reduction of new Nearly Zero-Energy Wooden buildings in the Northern Climatic Conditions.

"NERO" (6) is another project that stands out in the topics of wood construction. The main partners are the University of Aalto, the University of Technology in Tallin, the circular economy company Kovula Innovation Oy, the SINTEF Research Institute and the municipality of Växjö. The project started in 2017 and will end in September 2020. The project develops and demonstrates a design process and supply models for nearly zero energy wooden buildings with reduced costs for large-scale use in the climatic conditions of northern Europe and near zero performance (nZEB) and beyond. The project promotes the large-scale adoption on the market of the developed near zero energy wooden building applicable for the

design and procurement process of the building industry. The project wants to show the cost reduction of nearly zero-energy wooden buildings through demonstration projects that include both residential and non-residential individual buildings. The project aims to collect data from 11 cases of existing buildings representing educational and residential multi-family buildings and to conduct more detailed construction cost and life-cycle cost analyses for 6 demonstration buildings, including NZEB districts. The current result of the project is, in addition to an awareness campaign implemented through several workshops in the four countries of the project partners (Finland, Estonia, Norway and Sweden), a thorough analysis of both heating and cooling system thermal standards and air quality standards. The project also highlighted the importance of a low environmental impact building and its Life Cycle Assessment, reporting data from 6 of the 11 buildings examined. The emissions of the production phase of the buildings considered according to ISO 14040/44 (ISO 14040 2006, ISO 14044 2006) for the principles and framework for the LCA methodology were then analysed and documented. EN 15978 has been adopted for the assessment of the performance of buildings. EN 15804 has been adopted for the basic standards of Environmental Product Declarations (EPD) for construction products.

2.2.3 Build-in-Wood: Sustainable Wood Value Chain for Construction of Low-Carbon Multi-Storey Buildings from Renewable Resources.

"Build-in-Wood" (7) is another project in progress. The project started in 2019 and will end in 2022. 21 partners from 12 different countries have joined the project and it is coordinated by the Danish Technological Institute (DK). The project aims in the construction of multi-storey wooden buildings are: to make wood a natural choice of construction material for the construction of multi-storey buildings, to reduce the greenhouse gas emissions of the European construction sector, to establish an innovative and sustainable European value, to create a network for multi-storey wooden buildings. The project suggests: to optimize materials (resource efficiency, improved quality), develop a structural and customizable construction system platform and guidelines for the incorporation of ICT tools in the design process, produce educational, training and information tools on performance and environmental documentation of the materials, systems and solutions developed (e.g. LCA, LCC, S-LCA). It wants also to produce demonstration projects, disseminate stakeholder co-creation and plan scenario building workshops in selected European cities. "Build-in-Wood" also plans to increase training for entrepreneurs, SME and researchers, to create an open source design guide (for private clients and local/national authorities), to show the overview and to evaluate a relevant legislation, regulations and public standards.

2.3 European Cost-Action for the diffusion and study of the structural behavior of wood.

It is crucial to bring the attention also to three Cost Actions of wide adhesion and interest, in addition to the European projects listed previously.

2.3.1 Cost FP0702 - Net-Acoustics for Timber based Lightweight Buildings and Elements

"Cost Action FP0702" (8) involved 15 countries between 2008 and 2012. Compared to the projects analysed so far has a purely acoustic approach to timber construction. The main objective of the Action is to improve the acoustic behaviour of timber based lightweight buildings and to develop effective prediction models and measurement schemes. The main areas concerning the "FP0702" action are the airborne and impact sound performances and the sound from service equipment. In this study these are considered over a frequency range including low frequencies (50 to 100 Hz) due to the lightweight buildings attitude to have performances lower than in heavy buildings. The low frequency vibration (below 25 Hz, ISO 140) such as floor vibration due to people walking is also considered, particularly its perceptive aspect.

The approach methodology was to improve an effective sharing of research results and transfer of knowledge between research institutions, developing an overview of existing knowledge, defining goals and coordinating ongoing and new research activities at national and European level. A critical point it is also been to identifying research institutions who can/will apply for specific research funding and co-operating closely with the Standardization Committees CEN and ISO. Thanks to these expedients two main outcomes has been produced: several workshops to share the acoustic knowledge made available by the partners and an e-book. This latter document was accessible to all and explain, in accordance with the EN and ISO standards, the prediction methods, the measurement methods and the comfort assessment for sound and vibration performances. The acoustic design of lightweight timber frame constructions was also described.

2.3.2 Cost FP1102 - Assessment, Reinforcement and Monitoring of Timber Structures

"Cost Action FP1102" (9) involved 23 countries between 2011 and 2015. Compared to the projects analyzed so far has a purely structural approach to timber construction. The main objective of the action is to provide the necessary knowledge and methods to bring new developments in the timber construction sector into construction practice. This objective has been achieved through coordination, consolidation, harmonization and dissemination of research and development efforts aimed at improving existing rules or deriving new ones for the design of timber structures. To create a link between the principles of semi probabilistic design and recent advances in timber construction technology has been carried out:

- a framework and a procedure on how existing and new technologies can be implemented consistently in design formats
- the collection of information on advances in key technologies "Solid Wood", "Connections" and "Hybrid Timber Structures" in order to be implemented in structural design regulations
- the encouragement in communication and the optimization of collaboration between scientists, industry and all other stakeholders involved
- the promotion of complementary research, avoiding duplication of research and thus making better use of national and European funding resources.

2.3.3 Cost FP1402 - Basis of structural timber design - from research to standards

"Cost FP1402" (10) involved 27 countries from 2014 to 2018 addressing the issues of energy efficiency, knowledge dissemination and building systems. The objective of the action is to bridge the gap between widely available scientific results and the specific information needed by designers, industry, authorities and code committees, providing transfer for practical application in timber design and innovation. The action aims to achieve these purposes through the coordination, consolidation, harmonization and dissemination of recent research and development efforts aiming at improving existing design methods and rules or deriving new ones for wooden structures. This combination of actions increased the confidence of coders, authorities, designers and end-users in the safe, durable and efficient use of wood in structures and, consequently, will increase its acceptance and use in the design of buildings. The cost action of such broad adherence has resulted in the production of more than 45 relevant papers. Noteworthy were the outcomes on:

- construction details,
- simulations and assessments of strength,
- physical capabilities of wood building materials,
- new perspectives for wooden buildings in Europe in the seismic field in accordance with the EC8
- the proposal for a revision of the EC5 with the inclusion of the contents obtained from the Action.

The second main success of Action FP1402 was the creation and expansion of a strong network of practitioners from academia and practice. This has been witnessed not only by the high participation in thematic conferences, but also by the high production of training and educational materials.

3. Discussion

Basing on what has been described and analysed, it can be seen that BIGWOOD's intention is in line with the European plan for: the dissemination of the wood supply chain, the dissemination of knowledge, the need to make clear the standards of European standards for multi-story wooden buildings and the analysis of the cost benefits of these types of buildings.

It can be seen that, from a comparison with the projects analysed in the Section 2.1, there is a clear need to develop awareness on the realization of multi-story wooden buildings throughout Europe. This intent requires the involvement of many neighbouring countries to achieve a close collaboration and an optimized development of regional resources. BIGWOOD's contribution in first place will be to establish a wood supply chain between Austria and Italy.

By the comparison between BIGWOOD and the Section 2.2, is highlighted that it is increasingly essential at European level to understand which issues identified allow the reduction of costs and the assessment of environmental impacts. BIGWOOD wants also to improve the basis for a design that is as consistent as possible with the European nearly Energy Zero Building (nZEB) model that also respects the earthquake-proof and fire safety standards, which are fundamental for good design. Additionally, the BIGWOOD project wants to reduce the uncertainties not only on thermal standards, but also on acoustic standards, a delicate topic for timber construction, as shown by the results in Section 2.3.1.

BIGWOOD also aims to draw up clear and open source guidelines on: technical standards, the different technologies of wood construction and the different knowledge of the wood material available to partners, in accordance with what planned at European level showed in Section 2.3.

BIGWOOD project wants to concretize the theoretical aspects in a complex framework such as that of the design of multi-story wooden buildings. This wants to be achieved through the realization of three demonstration mock-ups: 1:20, a 1:5 and a 1:1 scale. All of them will be open to the public. In this way will be possible to show the technologies used, to raise awareness and to motivate the network of connection of the Italian-Austrian wood supply chain. In addition, will be redacted an open source document with the trace of what has been done and of the different technologies considered highlighting the main and tricky points of design and project execution. Will be also payed attention to the choice of local and natural materials, environmental impact and user comfort. The purpose will be to demonstrate the design value of wood building technology that is potentially competitive with the more widespread traditional technology.

Table 1: Summary table of the issues addressed by the different European projects analysed

	EURO WOOD IV	COOP WOD	KNOW WOOD	TRIPLE WOOD	FORMA WOOD	NERO	BUILD IN WOOD	C.A. FP 0702	C.A. FP 1102	C.A. FP 1402	BIG WOOD
Realization of the wood supply chain	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓				✓
Information and awareness	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓
Workshop		✓			✓	✓	✓	✓			✓
Didactic material	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Seismic and/or fire safety standards										✓	✓
Acoustic and/or thermal standards				✓		✓	✓				✓
Open Source Hand-book				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓
LCA					✓	✓					✓
Construction of a multi-story building											✓

4. Conclusions

From the analysis of the European plan done in the Section 2 emerges how the BIGWOOD project deals with many information and communication, social, educational and training issues. The new perspective of BIGWOOD lies in the realization of technical and theoretical dossiers through the apex of the project: the execution of a wooden multi-story building on a 1:1 scale and the drafting of an open source manual. This latter will be available not only to timber companies, designers and training facilities, but also to the interested audience. The openness of the project on different topics, the complex and ambitious structure are aimed at raising awareness and proposing a greater openness towards new construction technologies for wood. This without compromising the comfort of traditional buildings and promoting a vision with a lower environmental impact, compared to the most common traditional building techniques.

References

1. **(ERDF), Interact Co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund.** *keep.eu*. [Online] 2013 - 2017. <https://www.keep.eu/project/9220/interegional-test-and-promotion-centre-for-the-wood-sector>.
2. **CoopWood.** *coopwood.eu*. [Online] 2014 - 2020. <http://coopwood.eu/>.
3. **Region, EUSALP EU Strategy for the Alpine.** *triplewood.eu*. [Online] 2018-2020. <https://www.triplewood.eu/>.
4. **Union, Erasmus+Programme of the European.** *KnoWood*. [Online] 2019-2021. <https://knowood.eu/>.
5. **FormaWood.** [Online] 2014 - 2020. <https://www.formawood.eu/>.
6. **NERO.** NERO: Wood for Zero. [Online] 2017 - 2020. <https://neroproject.net/>.
7. **Build-in-Wood.** BUILD IN WOOD. [Online] 2019-2021. <https://www.build-in-wood.eu/>.
8. **COST European Cooperation in Science &Technology.** *cost.eu*. [Online] 2008-2012. <https://www.cost.eu/actions/FP0702/>.
9. —. *cost.eu*. [Online] 2011-2015. <https://www.cost.eu/cost-action/assessment-reinforcement-and-monitoring-of-timber-structures/#tabs{Name:parties}>.
10. **COST European Cooperation in Science &Technology;.** *cost.eu*. [Online] 2014-2018. <https://www.cost.eu/actions/FP1402/#tabs{Name:parties}>.